

Table S3 The values of optical band gap energy, Urbach energy, conduction band energy and valence band energy of pristine g-C₃N₄ and Na-modified g-C₃N₄ samples.

Samples	E _{bg} [eV]	E _U [meV]	E _{CB} [*] [eV]	E _{VB,XPS} [eV]
g-C ₃ N ₄	2.99	71.4	-1.43	+1.56
Na(0.01)-CN	2.95	81.1	-1.38	+1.57
Na(0.02)-CN	2.94	82.7	-1.34	+1.60

* Values of E_{CB} were calculated from E_{VB,XPS} and E_{bg}.